

Revealing Catalytic Properties of Palladium/Gold Systems towards Hydrogen Evolution, Oxidation, and Absorption with Scanning Electrochemical Microscopy

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*Christian M. Schott,¹ Julia Holl,¹ Raul Zazpe,^{2,3} Michael Kopp,¹ Ondřej Man,² Sitaramanjaneya M. Thalluri,^{2,3} Jhonatan Rodriguez-Pereira,^{2,3} Peter M. Schneider,¹ Kun-Ting Song,¹ Emre Keles,¹ Pekka Peljo,⁴ Jerzy Jasielec,^{4,5} Elena L. Gubanova,^{*1} Jan M. Macak,^{*2,3} Aliaksandr S. Bandarenka^{*1,6}*

1 - Physics of Energy Conversion and Storage, Technical University of Munich, James Franck

Str. 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

2 - Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123,

61200 Brno, Czech Republic

3 - Center of Materials and Nanotechnologies, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of

Pardubice, Nam. Cs. Legii 565, 53002 Pardubice, Czech Republic

4 -Research Group of Battery Materials and Technologies, Department of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Turku, 20014 Turun

Yliopisto, Finland

5 – Department of Physical Chemistry and Modelling, Faculty of Materials Science and Ceramics, AGH University of Science and Technology, Al. Mickiewicza 30, 30-059 Kraków,

Poland

6 - Catalysis Research Center TUM, Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Str. 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

* Corresponding author emails: elena.gubanova@tum.de, jan.macak@upce.cz,
bandarenka@ph.tum.de

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ABSTRACT

Palladium (Pd) serves as a versatile catalyst for various reactions, including hydrogen evolution (HER) and hydrogen oxidation (HOR) reactions, due to its favorable adsorption energy for atomic hydrogen. Its binding energy can be optimized by modifying the d-band center of the Pd through strain and ligand effects *via* Pd deposition onto suitable substrates like gold (Au). In this study, we employed scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) to investigate the HER and HOR properties of Pd/Au systems. A sub-monolayer of Pd (Pd_{ML}) was electrochemically deposited onto a polycrystalline (pc) Au substrate via underpotential deposition (UPD). Sample generation - tip consumption (SG-TC) mode experiments were conducted for the HER, revealing a significantly higher HER activity of the Pd atoms in the proximity of the Pd/Au border. For an in-depth analysis, a set of Pd/Au samples with increasing density of such Pd/Au borders was synthesized using Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD). These ALD Pd deposits with increased thickness - compared to a sub-monolayer - were investigated toward the HOR to minimize hydride formation, which results in the reconstruction of the Pd (sub)surface. Here, we highlight the influence of cations in 0.1 M AMOH (AM = Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺) electrolytes on the HOR/H-absorption activity, using the redox competition SECM mode (RC-SECM). Interestingly, the activity increases with a larger cation size and lower hydration energies in the following sequence: $j_{\text{LiOH}} < j_{\text{NaOH}} < j_{\text{KOH}} < j_{\text{RbOH}} < j_{\text{CsOH}}$. Additional laser-induced current transient (LICT) experiments supported these findings, confirming the trend between employed cation and electrocatalytic activity observed with RC-SECM.

INTRODUCTION

Palladium (Pd) can catalyze a variety of reactions, including the oxidation of methane,¹ methanol,^{2,3} ethanol,⁴ and formic acid⁵. Additionally, Pd plays an important role in the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER)⁶ and hydrogen oxidation reaction (HOR)⁷ due to its almost ideal, slightly negative adsorption energy of atomic hydrogen.^{8,9} However, the slightly stronger binding energy limits the rate of the HER/HOR by the desorption of the reaction products.^{9,10} Besides material composition, several other factors, including crystal orientation, surface roughness, or support materials, may also influence the hydrogen adsorption energy.^{9,11} Furthermore, the formation of bulk alloys seems to modify the binding energies through strain and ligand effects, whereas strain effects primarily shift adsorption energies for thin films thicker than three atomic layers due to the absence of ligand effects.¹² These observations have led to studies of thin Pd films deposited on single crystal substrates^{13,14} to modify the hydrogen adsorption energy by shifts of the d-band center of Pd.¹⁵ For example, Liang et al.¹⁶ employed electrochemical scanning tunneling microscopy (EC-STM) experiments to reveal that the most active sites are populated at the boundary between two-dimensional Pd clusters and the Au substrate. Their work suggested to maximize the number of such two-dimensional Pd clusters to achieve a maximal reaction activity for the HER. However, if the thickness of the Pd deposits on Au increases, hydride formation becomes thermodynamically viable,¹⁷ also known as the absorption of atomic hydrogen into the Pd crystal structure. Viola et al.¹⁸ reported that hydride formation occurs for potentials below approximately 0.3 V vs. the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) in 0.1 M HClO₄ at 25°C for Pd/C nanostructures and becomes more pronounced for more cathodic potentials. Regarding Pd deposits on Au, the threshold potential at which hydrogen absorbs into the crystal structure could depend crucially on the employed electrolyte and the thickness of the Pd deposit on the Au substrate.

In this work, we employ scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM) to investigate such Pd/Au systems for the HER and HOR reactions. For exploring the HER, a Pd sub-monolayer (Pd_{ML}) was electrochemically deposited on polycrystalline (pc) Au to study the HER activity using the sample generation tip collection (SG-TC) mode.^{19,20,21,22,23} In this mode, the Pd/Au substrate is polarized to evolve molecular hydrogen, while the HOR takes place at the microelectrode. The larger the measured HOR current at the microelectrode tip, the greater the local HER activity of the catalyst sample. Furthermore, Pd nanoclusters with different lateral sizes, thicknesses, and loadings were deposited on Au(pc) using Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD). Since the thickness of the Pd clusters exceeds several monolayers of Pd, significant hydride formation will be thermodynamically feasible under HER conditions. Although it is known that hydride formation in Pd improves the HER activity,²⁷ degradation of the (sub)surface Pd layer takes place due to hydride-induced surface reconstructions under reaction conditions.²⁴ This morphological reconstruction emerges due to the interaction of the diffusing hydrogen atoms with the respective Pd atoms within the crystal structure.²⁵ STM has been used to investigate surface reconstructions in ultra-high vacuum (UHV)²⁶ and under electrochemical conditions.²⁷ The high-resolution images in UHV conditions of Pd(110) reveal (1x2) missing-row structures originating from upper and lower terraces.²⁸ EC-STM measurements for low-indexed Pd single crystals in 0.1 M HClO₄ illustrate formations of hills, islands, and other hydride-induced morphological defects.²⁴ To minimize such structural modification, we investigated the Pd nanopillar deposits on Au(pc) for the HOR since, at those potentials, the extent of hydride formation will be less significant, as highlighted in reference 18.

While HOR measurements are often performed via tip-generation sample collection (TG-SC) mode,^{29,30,31,32} significant background currents on larger conductive substrates typically complicate visualizing electrocatalytic regions with varying activity.^{33,34} To avoid these

limitations, the redox competition mode (RC-SECM) was developed in 2006 and is now considered the state-of-the-art method for investigating the local activity and selectivity of the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) towards H_2O or H_2O_2 .^{33,35,36} In this work, to the best of our knowledge, we employ the RC-SECM mode to investigate HOR for the first time. The accuracy of the mode allows for the elucidation of the cation influence on the HOR activity in 0.1 M AMOH (AM = Li^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+). An evaluation method was developed that provides a parameter that quantifies the HOR/H absorption activity in the measured localized area by RC-SECM.

To prove the observed cation influence on the HOR activity, laser-induced current transient technique (LICT) measurements were performed on electrochemically deposited sub- Pd_{ML} on Au(pc) and Au(111). The LICT technique allows for the estimation of the so-called potential of maximum entropy (PME), a parameter related to the structure of the electrochemical double layer formed at the catalyst material under defined conditions. Studies showed that the closer the PME is positioned to the thermodynamic equilibrium potential of the electrocatalytic reaction, the more active this reaction seems to be.^{37,38,39} Our LICT experiments predict the same cation trend on the electrocatalytic activity as our developed RC-SECM, suggesting an increased HOR activity with increasing cation size ($\text{Cs}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$). The observed trend is in contrast to the HER trend reported by Bender et al.,⁴⁰ detected for a bulk Pd(pc) disc, where the highest activities were obtained with decreasing cation size ($\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$). The different trend indicates the crucial role of Pd atoms in the vicinity of the Pd/Au border,¹⁶ whose d-band structure is shifted due to strain and ligand effects from the underlying Au(pc) substrate.

METHOD SECTION

2.1 Microelectrode fabrication and characterization

Microelectrodes were fabricated in-house using a mechanical puller (Sensolytics, Germany) to form conical glass tips from 1.5 mm capillaries. A Pt wire (25 μm diameter, 99.95% metals basis, Alfa Aesar) was then inserted into the conical glass tip and sealed by heating it with a coil. For the electrical connection, a lacquered Cu wire (0.5 mm diameter, grade 2, SchneiTec), with both ends free of insulation, was soldered to the Pt wire using Sn_{96.5}Ag₃Cu_{0.5} solder (0.5 mm diameter, Felder Löttechnik). The tip was polished on sandpaper to obtain a disk-shaped microelectrode. The glass-to-Pt ratios, ranging from 6 to 10, were determined by optical microscopy, similar to the microelectrodes reported in reference 41. Prior to any electrocatalytic experiments, the microelectrode was polished and characterized to ensure consistent conditions across distinct experiments. The polishing involved using Al₂O₃ paste of three particle sizes: 5 μm , 1 μm , and 0.3 μm and silicon dioxide particles of 0.03 μm size (Sensolytics, Germany). After each polishing step, the tip was rinsed multiple times with deionized water (18.2 M Ω cm, Stakpure, Germany) and ethanol (absolute for analysis, EMSURE® ACS). Furthermore, between each polishing step, the tip was immersed in an ultrasonic bath (Bandelin) to remove any remaining Al₂O₃ and silicon dioxide particles from the Pt surface. Following the polishing and cleaning of the microelectrode, it was electrochemically characterized in a redox mediator containing 5 mM potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) trihydrate K₄[Fe(CN)₆] · 3H₂O (99.95% trace metals basis, Sigma Aldrich) and 100 mM potassium chloride KCl (99.99% trace metals basis, Sigma Aldrich). Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed to validate a successful fabrication and cleaning procedure by sweeping the potential from -0.2 V to 0.5 V vs. a silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) reference

electrode using a potentiostat (VSP-300, Bio-Logic, France). The diffusion-limited current, established through the oxidation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ to $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$, was used to determine the suitability of the microelectrode. For a 25 μm Pt electrode, theoretically, a plateau at 15.6 nA is expected, while slightly higher values emerge under experimental conditions. Only microelectrodes exhibiting similar diffusion-limited currents were selected to ensure consistent electrocatalytic behavior in subsequent SECM experiments.

2.2 SECM setup

For all conducted SECM (Sensolytics, Germany) experiments, a bipotentiostat from Autolab (PGSTAT302N) was used. The microelectrode characterization in a KCl electrolyte with $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was performed in an acrylic glass cell (Sensolytics, Germany). Electrochemical measurements involving HClO_4 , or AMOH ($\text{AM} = \text{Li}^+, \text{Na}^+, \text{K}^+, \text{Rb}^+, \text{Cs}^+$) were conducted in a PEEK cell. In the acrylic glass cell, a curled miniature Pt counter electrode (Sensolytics, Germany) was employed, while the PEEK cell utilized a Pt net counter electrode. Both cells used a Ag/AgCl reference electrode containing a 3 M KCl filling electrolyte. The microelectrode was attached to the SECM stepper stage, permitting movement in all three dimensions. The setup was configured as either a three-electrode or four-electrode system depending on the specific electrochemical experiment.

2.3 Electrolytes

Before any experiments, the SECM cells were flushed multiple times with boiled, deionized water. To explore the electrocatalytic properties of the Pd/Au sample in different electrolytes, all electrochemical measurements for each sample were always performed above the same area. Between measurements, the previous electrolyte was removed, and the cell was flushed multiple

times with deionized water before the next electrolyte was filled into the cell. In the PEEK cell, six different electrolytes were used: 0.1 M HClO₄ (70% HClO₄, extra pure, Acros) and 0.1 M AMOH (AM = Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺). For the hydroxide electrolytes, 100 ml solutions were prepared by dissolving approximately 0.24 g of LiOH powder (anhydrous, 99.995% metals basis, Alfa Aesar), 0.4 g of NaOH pellets (semiconductor grade, 99.99% trace metals basis, Sigma Aldrich), and 0.56 g of KOH pellets (semiconductor grade, 99.99% trace metals basis, Sigma Aldrich), respectively, in deionized water. For RbOH and CsOH, solutions with 50 wt.% in H₂O and 99% trace metals basis (Sigma Aldrich) were used, with volumes of 1.178 ml and 1.743 ml, respectively. Similar electrolytes were used for the LICT experiments.

2.4 Underpotential deposition of a Pd sub-monolayer onto an Au substrate

For the underpotential deposition of a Pd sub-monolayer, a glass cell was used, which was previously cleaned using the Caro's Acid, a 3:1 mixture of sulfuric acid (96% H₂SO₄, Suprapur, Merck, Germany) and hydrogen peroxide (30% H₂O₂, p.a., ISO, Carl Roth, Germany). The Caro's Acid remained in the glass cell for approximately 12 hours before the cell was extensively washed with boiled deionized water. The cell was equipped with a mercury/mercurous sulfate reference electrode (Si Analytics, Germany) and a curled Pd counter electrode. The Pd underpotential deposition measurement followed the procedure outlined in reference 42. Initially, PdCl₂ was dissolved in concentrated HCl to form an H₂PdCl₄ solution. This solution was then mixed with 0.1 M H₂SO₄ to prepare the deposition electrolyte containing 0.1 M H₂SO₄ and 0.1 mM H₂PdCl₄. Subsequently, the clean Au substrates were subjected to Pd UPD by linear sweep voltammetry from approximately 0.94 V to 0.26 V vs. RHE at a scan rate of 1 mV s⁻¹ in a previously Ar-purged electrolyte. Two different Au substrates were used: a polycrystalline Au quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) chip (Stanford Research Systems) and an Au(111) disk electrode (diameter:

10 mm, 99.999%, MaTecK, Jülich, Germany). For the Au(111) single crystal, annealing was conducted in a tubular furnace (Heraeus Instruments RO 7/50). The crystal was placed into a small ceramic boat, and the furnace was purged with Ar gas for 15 minutes at a flow rate of 150 ml min⁻¹. Subsequently, the crystal was heated up to 450°C for 20 minutes and then cooled down, reducing the gas flow to 80 ml min⁻¹. To validate the successful annealing procedure, CVs with a potential range from 0.52 to 1.72 V vs. RHE were recorded in Ar-saturated (99.999% purity, Air Liquide) 0.1 M HClO₄ at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹.

2.5 Atomic Layer Deposition of Pd films on Au(pc)

Au(pc) substrates were cleaned before ALD processes by dipping them in an ultrasonic bath in acetone, isopropanol, and distilled water for 5 minutes at each and dried with N₂ flow. Pd was deposited onto Au(pc) using an ALD tool (thermal ALD, TFS 200, Beneq). Palladium(II) hexafluoroacetylacetonate (min. 95%, Strem) and formaldehyde (36-38%) were used as the precursor and co-reactant, respectively. Under these deposition conditions, one ALD cycle was defined by the following sequence: Pd pulse (500 ms) - exposure time (10 s) - N₂ purge (20 s) - formaldehyde pulse (1 s) - exposure time (10 s) - N₂ purge (20 s). The number of ALD cycles applied was 600, 1000, and 1600, respectively (to induce the formation of Pd nanopillars of different sizes and coverage). All processes were carried out at a temperature of 200 °C, using N₂ (99.9999%) as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 400 sccm.

2.6 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) analyses were carried out by field-emission SEM JEOL JSM 7500F operated at 5 kV using an in-lens detector with the combined secondary electron as well as back-scattered electron imaging contributions. Dimensions of Pd nanopillars were obtained by the statistical analyses of SEM images using proprietary Nanomeasure software and using at least 30 counts for each sample ($n \geq 30$).

2.7 Electron Back Scatter Diffraction (EBSD)

EBSD analyses were conducted using an SEM-FIB system FEI Helios 660 G3 at 25 kV accelerating voltage and 1.6 nA beam current. The original analyzed area was $8 \mu\text{m} \times 16 \mu\text{m}$ with a 10 nm step. The collected diffraction data had to be cropped to $8 \mu\text{m} \times \sim 10 \mu\text{m}$ to compensate the effect of drift. EBSD data were treated in OIM Analysis 8 (EDAX) software by reindexing and pattern reconstruction to mitigate the effect of the very fine size of the Au/Pd particles.

2.8 X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

To verify the surface chemical composition of the Pd deposited by ALD, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis was performed using Scienta-Omicron (ESCA-2SR) instrument, with Al-K α monochromatic X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.69 \text{ eV}$). The acquired spectra were further fitted using CasaXPS software and referenced to the Au⁰ species centered at 84.0 eV, in order to perform the binding energy scale correction. Pd 3d spectra were fitted with asymmetric Lorentzian function

LA (1.10, 1.8, 120) for the metallic state (Pd^0) and mixed Gaussian-Lorentzian functions GL (30) for Pd oxides and Pd plasmon loss.

2.9 SECM experimental procedure

Before approaching the sample with the microelectrode tip, the microelectrode was cleaned and electrochemically activated by executing CVs in 0.1 M HClO_4 , with a potential range from -0.02 V to 1.3 V vs. RHE at a scan rate of 0.1 V s^{-1} , and potential steps of 0.01 V. The microelectrode was first manually approached and then further positioned using the stepper motor of the SECM device. Approximately 0.47 V vs. RHE was applied to the microelectrode in 0.1 M HClO_4 under air-saturated conditions. At this potential, the ORR occurs at the tip of the microelectrode. By approaching the microelectrode at a speed of $2 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ and in increments of $2 \mu\text{m}$, a continuous decrease in the ORR current was observed due to the blocked oxygen diffusion to the microelectrode as the tip-to-sample distance decreased. When the current dropped below 1 nA, the approach increment was reduced to $1 \mu\text{m}$ with a speed of $1 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$. The low increments and approaching speeds were chosen to ensure that the tip is not destroyed by slightly touching the surface of the sample, indicated by a sudden large, recorded current. The microelectrode was then retracted by $10 \mu\text{m}$ to establish a fixed and well-known tip-to-sample distance. The samples were cleaned and activated in 0.1 M HClO_4 before the SECM experiments. The potential ranges in the respective CVs corresponded to 0.1 V to 0.6 V vs. RHE with a scan rate of 0.1 V s^{-1} and potential steps of 0.01 V. For all array scan measurements, an increment of $12.5 \mu\text{m}$ and a maximum speed of $12.5 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$ were used. The waiting time between measurements corresponds to 25 ms during the SG-TC experiments and 100 ms for the RC-SECM measurements. For the SG-TC experiments, the microelectrode potential was set to 0.04 V vs. RHE, while the sample potential was set to 0.015

V vs. RHE. Due to air-saturated electrolyte conditions, the equilibrium potential of the HER/HOR was slightly Nernstian shifted, resulting in the production of molecular hydrogen at slightly positive potentials versus the RHE scale. Different potential pulses were used for the redox competition (RC) experiments, and their purposes are discussed in the results section. The RC experiments for different electrolytes were conducted over the same area of the respective Pd nanopillar sample. During the exchange procedure of the electrolytes, the position of the microelectrode was maintained, allowing measurements of the same area of the sample across different electrolytes to ensure ideal conditions for activity comparison. For completeness, it should be noted that for experiments with the Pd nanopillar sample after 1000 ALD cycles, a tilt correction was employed using the piezo scanning stage of the SECM.

2.10 Laser-Induced Current Transient technique

For LICT experiments, a glass cell, consisting of a preconditioning cell and a main compartment, was used. This cell also utilized a mercury/mercurous sulfate reference electrode and a Pt wire as a counter electrode. Additionally, the Pd_{ML}/Au sample was integrated into a Teflon holder and positioned in front of the laser window, where the laser beam (Quanta-Ray INDI Pulsed Nd:YAG laser, Spectra-Physics, USA) was pulsed during the LICT experiment. The preconditioning and main cells were washed several times with boiled deionized water, followed by cold water before experiments. The electrolyte was purged with Ar for 15 minutes in the preconditioning cell before being transferred to the main compartment, where it was purged for another 15 minutes. During the LICT experiments, the current was recorded by changing the applied potential in 0.02 V steps within the double-layer potential region. At each potential point, the pulsed laser beam illuminated

the surface of the working electrode ($\Delta t = 8$ ns, $f = 10$ Hz, $P = 150$ mW) for 4 seconds. The potential was swept three times between the potential vertices to ensure reproducibility. The potential range slightly varied: for 0.1 M LiOH, NaOH, and KOH, the range was 0.53 to 0.71 V vs. RHE; for RbOH and CsOH, the range was adjusted to 0.47 to 0.71 V and 0.43 to 0.67 V vs. RHE, respectively.

To correct for background noise, the median value was subtracted from the recorded current transients. Selected peaks were then integrated over time to obtain the charge associated with interfacial water reorientation and specific adsorption. The charge values for the respective potentials recorded during the LICT measurements were plotted against the respective potentials. The intersection points with the x-axis, determined from linear fits through all measurement points, estimated the PME for the respective working electrode in the measured electrolyte.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A sub-monolayer of Pd was deposited onto half of an Au(pc) substrate via underpotential deposition (UPD)⁴² to explore the electrocatalytic HER activity of Pd on Au and to investigate if Pd in the proximity of the Pd/Au boundary exhibits a significantly higher activity, as proposed by Liang et al.¹⁶ **Figure 1a** depicts a CV of the synthesized Pd_{ML} on Au(111) in 0.1 M HClO₄, revealing faradaic peaks arising from hydrogen underpotential deposition (H_{upd}), Pd-O/OH formation and reduction. **Figure 1b** illustrates a schematic of the synthesized sample along with an overview of the conducted experimental procedure. This procedure relies on a classical SG-TC mode, which was employed at the step between the deposited Pd layer and the Au(pc) substrate to reveal their distinct electrocatalytic activities. In this method, a potential of +15 mV vs. RHE is applied at the sample to induce H₂ evolution, while the microelectrode is polarized at +40 mV vs. RHE to oxidize the hydrogen generated at the sample locally. The resulting HOR microelectrode current allows for the indirect investigation of the HER activity of the sample. Areas with higher HER activity generate more H₂ molecules, resulting in higher HOR microelectrode currents and vice versa. The results of the SG-TC experiment for the Pd/Au system are displayed in **Figure 1c**. In agreement with the prediction, the HOR microelectrode current measured above the Pd layer clearly exceeds the current detected above Au. The two- and three-dimensional activity maps reveal a pronounced transition in current at the border between the Pd overlayer and the Au substrate. Furthermore, the first 200 μm adjacent to the Pd/Au border exhibits the highest electrocatalytic HER activity, which diminishes with increasing distance from the border. The higher activity at the Pd/Au border aligns with the previous results from Liang et al.,¹⁶ who identified the boundary between the Pd and Au substrate as the position of the most active sites. The enhanced HER activity up to a distance of ~200 μm from the Pd/Au border might be explained

by a broadening effect of the produced H_2 at the sample since $25\ \mu\text{m}$ microelectrodes were employed, which were positioned $10\ \mu\text{m}$ above the sample. Furthermore, the activity map reveals several defects within the deposited Pd layer, indicated by small circular areas with smaller currents. This observation suggests that the Pd deposition was not entirely homogenous upon the Au(pc) substrate.

Figure 1. (a) A typical CV of the Pd_{ML} deposited on Au(111), recorded in Ar-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄ at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. (b) Schematic representation of the employed SG-TC mode at the interface between the deposited Pd and Au(pc) used to study HER activities in air-saturated 0.1 M HClO₄. Air-saturated electrolytes lead to a Nernstian potential shift, allowing for a hydrogen evolution reaction onset at an already slightly positive potential vs. RHE. (c) Two- and three-dimensional HOR microelectrode current maps revealing the activity difference between the Pd and Au regions, as well as surface defects.

In the literature, it is well known that hydride formation does not occur in the case of a single Pd monolayer.¹⁷ As the Pd layer thickness increases, H absorption, leading to hydride formation, becomes more apparent. While it has been demonstrated that the binding energy of the adsorbed hydrogen atom changes favorably with an increasing number of palladium hydride sublayers,²⁷ morphological reconstruction arises because of the interaction between diffusing hydrogen atoms and Pd atoms within the crystal structure.²⁵ A recent study under electrochemical conditions showed the formation of islands, hills, and other hydride-induced surface structures on low-indexed Pd single crystals using EC-STM.²⁴ To minimize morphological changes of the Pd samples fabricated via ALD, we focus on the HOR since hydride formation seems to occur less significantly under these conditions.¹⁸ Here, the RC-SECM mode was employed, in which the microelectrode serves as an additional working electrode, producing locally a small amount of molecular H₂. Consequently, the local insertion of small amounts of reactants (molecular H₂) results in the hydrogen oxidation reaction and only minimal hydride formation at the Pd sample, evident by small faradaic currents measured for short time scales. These considerations are crucial for the Pd/Au system to reduce hydride-induced morphological modifications, thereby enabling the study of complex electrocatalytic processes. To be more precise, **Figure 2a** depicts the RC-SECM mode employed to study the HOR/H absorption reaction. As shown, different potential pulses are applied to the microelectrode, including conditioning, ORR, HER, and HOR pulses. First, the conditioning pulse is applied for 1 s in a potential regime, where minor faradaic processes occur, allowing the system to establish equilibrium conditions, such as recovering from local pH gradients in the electrolyte. During the second pulse, local oxygen is reduced for 1 s in the electrolyte near the tip and the sample area of interest. After the local removal of oxygen, its diffusion toward the investigated local area is significantly hindered due to the small tip-to-sample

separation distance of $\sim 10\mu\text{m}$. In the third pulse, molecular H_2 is generated within the electrolyte encapsulated between the tip and the sample for 0.4 s. The time and the respective potential were empirically determined and optimized to prevent H_2 bubble formation between the microelectrode and sample. It is important to note that molecular H_2 can be produced even at slightly positive potentials versus the RHE scale due to small Nernstian potential shifts arising from the non-entirely hydrogen-saturated electrolyte. In the fourth pulse, the molecular hydrogen, induced previously during the third pulse, is consumed at the microelectrode via HOR. The activity of HOR and H absorption at the sample is studied by applying an HOR/H absorption potential to the sample of interest during all mentioned microelectrode pulses. During the fourth pulse of 400 ms, the sample and the microelectrode compete to consume the previously induced molecular hydrogen. A small HOR microelectrode current indicates that the local area of the catalyst sample successfully competes against the microelectrode and consumes a significant amount of the induced molecular hydrogen. Conversely, a large HOR microelectrode current suggests a less active area of the sample, as the majority of the induced molecular hydrogen is consumed at the microelectrode. We can use this approach to differentiate areas of the Pd/Au sample with distinct electrocatalytic activity by monitoring the HOR current recorded at the microelectrode. By careful design of the experiment and reasonable data treatment, it is possible to create an HOR/H absorption activity map of the sample for each millisecond of the HOR microelectrode pulse. However, the HOR current during the fourth pulse declines rapidly after several milliseconds since the amount of previously induced molecular H_2 is small. These activity maps allow for the time-dependent visualization of differences in the local electrocatalytic activity. The resolution of the local electrocatalytic activity depends on several factors, such as the diameter of the employed microelectrode and tip-to-sample distance.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. (a) Schematic of the RC-SECM mode employed, illustrating the pulse profile at the microelectrode. Potentials for each pulse/sample bias in acidic and alkaline media are shown in red and blue, respectively. (b) SEM image of Pd nanopillars grown on Au(pc) via ALD. Increased synthesis cycles result in larger nanopillar sizes and higher Pd concentration.

To maximize the number of active sites at the boundary between Pd and Au, Pd nanopillars were grown onto a polycrystalline Au substrate using ALD, as depicted in **Figure 2b**. The Pd nanopillars' diameter varied, ranging from 14 ± 3 nm to 21 ± 4 nm and 26 ± 6 nm, depending on the number of ALD cycles - 600, 1000, and 1600 cycles, respectively. A detailed description of the ALD process can be found in the **Methods** section. Besides the nanopillar size, the overall Pd content and Pd surface coverage increase with more ALD cycles, as demonstrated in the survey XPS spectra of 600 and 1000 ALD cycles of Pd (**Figure S1a**). The presence of mainly metallic Pd is confirmed by the Pd 3d high-resolution XPS spectra (**Figure S1b and c**) since the binding energy of the spin-orbit splitting Pd 3d_{5/2} and Pd 3d_{3/2} is centered at ~ 335.3 and 340.6 eV,⁴³ respectively. As evident from **Figure 2b**, Pd-coated on Au(pc) with smaller cycling numbers display lower coverages and smaller film thicknesses, with an increased density of active Pd/Au borders accessible to the electrolyte. Due to the significantly larger microelectrode comprising a Pt wire with 25 μm diameter, it is not feasible to explore the electrocatalytic activity of individual Pd nanopillars. Instead, activity differences on the micrometer level can be detected, arising from the averaged electrocatalytic performance of the grown nanopillars. Furthermore, the RC-SECM method allows for the comparison of i) HOR/H absorption activity of the respective Pd nanopillar samples with distinct size and content in 0.1 M HClO₄ and ii) the influence of the employed cation in 0.1 M AMOH (AM = Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺) on the electrocatalytic activity. Nevertheless, to quantitatively study these phenomena, it is essential to consider the amount of molecular H₂ produced during the third microelectrode pulse, which directly influences the HOR current during the fourth pulse at the microelectrode and the HOR/H absorption current at the sample. Therefore, estimating the number of produced H₂ molecules from the third pulse is essential by integrating the recorded HER microelectrode current versus the time, as displayed in **Figure S2**. The Faradaic

charge Q_{HER} during the third pulse can then be divided by twice the electron charge to determine the number of produced H_2 . For completeness, we assume that the Faradaic current during the third pulse arises purely from the HER, given that all oxygen was removed during the second microelectrode pulse. As shown in **Figure S3**, the number of produced H_2 can be plotted in heat maps for the respective Pd samples in different electrolytes. Significant differences occur between different electrolytes but also within a single electrolyte. These differences suggest that the quantity of produced H_2 from the Pt microelectrode depends on three factors. First, the electrolyte itself influences the number of produced hydrogen molecules, as it is well known that the HER for Pt is drastically more active in acidic (0.1 M HClO_4) media compared to alkaline media (0.1 M AMOH).⁴⁴ Additionally, the utilized cation in AMOH electrolytes is known to influence HER activity due to the different hydration energies of the cation, affecting interfacial water and reaction kinetics.⁴⁰ Second, during all microelectrode pulses, the HOR/H absorption potential is applied to the Pd/Au sample. Due to the continuous consumption of molecular H_2 at the sample, the number of H_2 molecules produced at the tip can vary, according to the electrocatalytic HOR/H absorption activity of the local sample position. Third, the microelectrode-to-sample distance, and therefore the encapsulated electrolyte volume between tip and sample, significantly influences the amount of produced hydrogen molecules, as indicated by the variations within an individual heat map (**Figure S3**). The difference in tip-to-sample distance likely arises from sample tilt, inhomogeneities in Pd nanopillar distribution, or morphological surface changes. To correct the influence of produced H_2 molecules on the measured HOR current during the fourth pulse, the microelectrode HOR current recorded at each individual measurement increment needs to be normalized by the previously induced number of H_2 molecules produced at the same increment. Subsequently, the normalized HOR microelectrode current at each position can be plotted over

time into an activity map. It is only reasonable to create HOR activity maps for the first couple of milliseconds since the molecular H_2 concentration decreases with HOR measurement time. In the following, we discuss the electrocatalytic behavior of Pd deposits on Au(pc) toward the HOR and H absorption, as revealed by the RC-SECM mode. Exemplarily, the focus is set on the Pd nanopillars with an average diameter of $\sim 26 \pm 6$ nm to analyze the obtained results in 0.1 M $HClO_4$ and 0.1 M LiOH. Subsequently, we compare the HOR activity in acidic and alkaline media across all Pd nanopillar samples.

Figure 3 displays activity maps for the Pd nanopillars with $\sim 26 \pm 6$ nm diameter supported on Au(pc) during the first four milliseconds of pulse 4 in 0.1 M $HClO_4$ and 0.1 M LiOH. Small HOR microelectrode currents, normalized by the number of H_2 molecules indicated in blue, correspond to regions on the sample with higher electrocatalytic activity towards HOR/H absorption. In 0.1 M $HClO_4$, a few spots with high activity (blue color) initially exist at zero milliseconds. Within one to two milliseconds of the fourth pulse, additional low-current spots appear on the heat plots, while persisting spots expand or merge. Surprisingly, the background color of the heat maps becomes darker (green and blue color) compared to the initial heat map, indicating a global decrease in the HOR current normalized by the initially produced number of H_2 molecules. Two phenomena provide explanations for both observations. First, an activation process of the sample occurs, resulting in an increased density of active regions and a global increase in HOR/H absorption activity over time. Second, the previously induced molecular H_2 concentration decreases, either as it is steadily consumed as a reactant during the fourth pulse or as it diffuses into the bulk electrolyte (or both). This decrease in concentration leads to a global decline in the recorded HOR current at the microelectrode. It diminishes the activity contrast between regions with distinct electrocatalytic HOR/H absorption activity, seemingly causing an expansion of active regions.

After the measurement in 0.1 M HClO₄, activity measurements with different alkaline electrolytes were conducted in the same sample area, as explained in the experimental section. The heat maps on the right in **Figure 3** show the activity measurements of the $\sim 26 \pm 6$ nm Pd nanopillar sample at the same position in 0.1 M LiOH. Similar observations occur compared to the measurement in acidic media. Nevertheless, at 0 ms, most blue spots are detected at different positions compared to those in 0.1 M HClO₄. Only the active region at $x \sim 100\text{-}120$ μm and $y \sim -70$ to -90 μm appears for both electrolytes. One hypothesis is that different HOR/H absorption mechanisms in acidic and alkaline media lead to different regions being active for HOR/H absorption. Comparing the results in 0.1 M HClO₄ and 0.1 M LiOH reveals that the overall HOR-normalized currents in the alkaline regime are significantly lower than in acidic media. Additionally, the initially induced H₂ concentration decreases more slowly in 0.1 M LiOH, as suggested by the slower decrease in the background current over time. This underscores once more slower reaction kinetics of HOR/H absorption in alkaline media. An overview of activity maps in 0.1 M HClO₄ and AMOH electrolytes of the Pd sample with $\sim (26 \pm 6)$ nm nanopillars up to 5 ms can be found in **Figure S4 – S9**. Furthermore, animated videos highlighting the HOR activity changes in the respective electrolyte are presented in **Figure S10**.

Figure 3. RC-SECM activity maps for the Pd nanopillar sample grown on Au(pc) with an average diameter of 26 ± 6 nm. The heat maps display the HOR microelectrode current, normalized by the number of hydrogen molecules produced during the third pulse of RC-SECM. The plots on the left represent measurements in 0.1 M HClO₄, while those on the right show corresponding measurements in 0.1 M LiOH at identical sample locations. The time in the top right corner of each plot indicates the specific moment during the fourth pulse when the HOR current was recorded. The arrow on the right signifies that with increasing time, the previously induced H₂ concentration during the third pulse decreases, as evidenced by the color change in the heat maps.

In order to compare the electrocatalytic HOR/H absorption activity in various electrolytes for differently-sized Pd nanopillar samples, we developed an approach based on RC-SECM measurements that aims to quantify each contour plot through a parameter, which is directly correlated with the activity of the sample. Such a parameter can be obtained by performing surface integration of the normalized HOR current over the lateral coordinates. A smaller value suggests higher electrocatalytic HOR/H absorption activity, as a smaller microelectrode current in the contour plot corresponds to a larger activity of the catalyst sample area under investigation. Since molecular hydrogen present in the electrolyte between the microelectrode and the sample decreases rapidly, only parameter values obtained from the surface integration after the first millisecond were investigated. To validate this characterization concept, HOR/H absorption activity evaluations of the three different Pd nanopillar samples were conducted in 0.1 M HClO₄. Due to the nanopillar growth via ALD, controlling their size and Pd content independently appears to be impossible. This means that samples comprised of larger nanopillars inherently contain higher Pd content. However, comparing the three Pd nanopillar samples with distinct sizes and Pd content is ideal for proving the developed HOR/H absorption activity evaluation procedure, as samples consisting of larger nanopillars with higher Pd content are expected to exhibit greater HOR/H absorption activity. **Figure 4a** shows the values obtained for the surface integration of the normalized HOR microelectrode current for the first milliseconds of the three Pd nanopillar samples. A clear activity trend emerges, revealing that higher HOR/H absorption activities are achieved for samples with larger Pd nanopillars and higher Pd content, as predicted above, validating the developed HOR/H absorption activity procedure using SECM.

As will be shown in the following, this procedure facilitates the exploration of complex phenomena, such as the influence of the cation in 0.1 M AMOH (AM = Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺) on

the HOR/H absorption activity. **Figure 4b** depicts the activity measurements in 0.1 M AMOH for each individual cation across the three Pd nanopillar samples of distinct sizes. For the 14 ± 3 nm- and 21 ± 4 nm-sized Pd nanopillars, the HOR/H absorption activity consistently increases with increasing cation size, and therefore, decreasing hydration energy $j_{\text{LiOH}} < j_{\text{NaOH}} < j_{\text{KOH}} < j_{\text{RbOH}} < j_{\text{CsOH}}$. For the largest Pd nanopillars of 26 ± 6 nm, a similar tendency is observed; however, the HOR/H absorption activity in NaOH slightly exceeds that in KOH, i.e., $j_{\text{LiOH}} < j_{\text{KOH}} < j_{\text{NaOH}} < j_{\text{RbOH}} < j_{\text{CsOH}}$.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4. Integrated HOR microelectrode currents from HOR/H absorption array scans during RC-SECM experiments. The current was normalized by the number of hydrogen molecules produced during the third pulse. Integrated and normalized HOR microelectrode current for (a) Pd nanopillar samples with different sizes and Pd content in 0.1 M HClO₄ for the first 14 ms, and for (b) each individual sample explored in different 0.1 M AMOH (AM = Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺) electrolytes.

The question arises as to why the decreasing hydration energy of the cation correlates with an increase in the electrocatalytic HOR/H absorption activity of the samples. A recent study demonstrated that the HER activity of Pd increases with decreasing cation size and increasing hydration energy in 0.1 M AMOH electrolytes.⁴⁰ These findings are in strong contrast with the trend reported for Au, where increased HER activity is associated with larger cation size and smaller hydration energy.^{45,46} The reason appears to stem from the influence of the cations on the transition state of H₂O dissociation and its products, as mentioned by Bender et al.⁴⁰ and Monteiro et al.⁴⁵ Since water dissociation is rate-limiting in the case of Au, but not for Pd, a different trend emerges. Although this relationship between cation size and electrocatalytic activity has been explored for the HER in literature, a similar trend might emerge for the HOR, being the reverse reaction of the HER with the same pathways and intermediate.

The HOR/H absorption activity trend of the Pd nanopillars grown onto Au(pc), shown in **Figure 4**, aligns more closely with the expected trend for Au than with Pd in 0.1 M AMOH electrolytes. From our perspective, it is most likely that the d-band center of the Pd atoms in the vicinity of the Pd/Au borders is shifted due to the different lattice parameters of Pd and the Au substrate.^{15,17} Therefore, it is not a surprise that the observed cation trend in **Figure 4b** also depends on the coverage, lateral size, and thickness of the Pd nanopillar deposits on Au. The expected trend for Au is observed for the ALD samples with 600 and 1000 cycles, which consist of numerous Pd/Au border regions, due to their lower Pd coverage, as evident from the SEM image in **Figure 2b**. In contrast, for the 1600-cycle sample, the activity in NaOH exceeds that in KOH. This could be an indication of a larger Pd film thickness and coverage, making the influence of the d-band shifted Pd atoms in the proximity of the Pd/Au border less significant. Post-mortem, cross-sectional SEM imaging (**Figure 5a**) of the Pd-coated Au(pc) (with 1600c) at the area of electrochemical

characterization supports this hypothesis. It shows a continuous but rough and porous Pd layer onto which numerous Pd nanopillars are grown. The overall thickness of this layer is approximately 45 nm with a standard deviation of ± 6 nm, due to the nanopillars making the upper part of the layer rougher. Moreover, the AFM roughness measurements of this sample (**Figure 5b**) compared to the uncoated Au(pc) sample (**Figure S11**) confirm the presence of Pd nanopillars (with a height of approx. 10-20 nm) that are protruding from the underlying Pd layer. Due to the nanopillar diameter of $\sim (26 \pm 6)$ nm, the electrolyte still has access to the d-band shifted Pd atoms in the proximity of the Pd/Au border. However, despite Pd atoms at the interface having proven to be the most active,¹⁶ the Na⁺ containing AMOH displays a higher activity than the one with K⁺, according to the behavior of bulk Pd.

Furthermore, post-mortem electron backscatter diffraction mapping (EBSD) was carried out on the Pd sample with 1600 ALD cycles (**Figure 5c**) in comparison to the reference Au(pc) substrate (**Figure S12**). The EBSD data were affected by the very fine size of the Au crystallites and, therefore, the large proportion of grain boundaries in the analyzed areas. Grain boundaries generally yield low-quality diffraction data, so only the higher confidence part of the datasets was used to generate inverse pole figure (IPF) maps. **Figure 5c and S12** show the amount of data disregarded because of this effect. **Figure S13** illustrates the crystallographic texture of the Au and Au + Pd particles. The most prominent component in both cases is the almost perfect alignment of (111) directions with the Au(pc) normal, i.e., the Au or Au + Pd crystallites have their (111) planes exposed in parallel with the surface. Pd deposited on the Au(pc) seems to follow the same crystallographic orientation, validating that RC-SECM measurement did not result in significant reconstruction of the Pd nanopillars.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5. Post-mortem (a) cross-sectional SEM, (b) AFM roughness measurements, and (c) EBSD of the Pd-coated Au(pc) sample (with 1600c) at the area of electrochemical characterization.

To further explore whether the inverted cation trend for Pd arises from the influence of the underlying Au substrate, LICT experiments were conducted to determine the so-called PME of the Pd/Au system. The PME is closely related to the orientation of interfacial water within the electrochemical double layer and corresponds to the potential at which maximal disorder occurs.³⁷ Especially in alkaline media, the structure of interfacial water is believed to crucially influence reaction kinetics, as the rearrangement of water dipoles after electron transfer necessitates further energy.^{37,47} All experimental results obtained from LICT measurements suggest that the closer the PME is positioned to the thermodynamic equilibrium potential of the electrochemical reaction, the more electrocatalytically active the reaction appears to be.⁴⁸ This indicates that the PME functions as a descriptor to predict reaction kinetics, even though a fundamental theory correlating the PME with reaction kinetics is still under development.

Since LICT experiments require smooth samples to perform experiments, and the influence of the Au substrate on Pd/Au system is most significant for thin layers, all LICT experiments were conducted with a Pd_{ML} deposited on Au(pc) and Au(111) using the UPD method. Exemplary surface charge dependencies on the applied potential during LICT measurement in 0.1 M AMOH electrolytes for the Pd_{ML}/Au(111) system are provided in **Figure S14 – S18**. **Figure 6** displays the observed PME trends depending on the employed cation in 0.1 M AMOH electrolytes for the Pd_{ML}/Au(pc) and Pd_{ML}/Au(111) samples. Both systems demonstrate a decreasing PME trend with increasing cation size and decreasing hydration energies. The closer the PME is positioned to the equilibrium potential of HER/HOR/H absorption, the higher the activity of the Pd_{ML}/Au(pc) and Pd_{ML}/Au(111) systems in the respective electrolyte. Therefore, from LICT experiments, it can be predicted that the HER/HOR/H absorption activity trend corresponds to: $j_{\text{LiOH}} < j_{\text{NaOH}} < j_{\text{KOH}} <$

$j_{\text{RbOH}} < j_{\text{CsOH}}$. These predicted activities from LICT align perfectly with the HOR/H absorption activity observed by SECM for the Pd nanopillars, validating our developed RC-SECM approach.

Figure 6. PME determined from LICT as a function of the hydration energy of alkali metal cations in 0.1 M AMOH electrolytes for Pd monolayers deposited on either Au(pc) or Au(111). The arrows on the right indicate that the PME in 0.1 M CsOH is positioned closest to the equilibrium potential of the HER/HOR and, therefore, should exhibit the highest reaction activity.

CONCLUSION

Pd deposits on Au have been proven to shift the adsorption energy of atomic hydrogen beneficially due to a modified d-band center of Pd emerging from strain and ligand effects. However, the Pd/Au system encounters significant stability issues under operando HER/HOR conditions due to hydride formation. For thin Pd films deposited on Au, hydride formation is thermodynamically suppressed, facilitating the study of the Pd's electrocatalytic properties for the HER. Furthermore, SG-TC experiments revealed that the Pd atoms in the proximity of the Pd/Au border show enhanced electrocatalytic HER activity, validating results with EC-STM experiments in the literature.

More complex Pd structures were grown on an Au(pc) substrate using the ALD. Due to the differently sized Pd nanopillars, the samples were characterized for the HOR since hydride formation occurs less significantly under these reaction conditions. The employed RC-SECM procedure, with our developed data treatment procedure, revealed a temporal HOR/H absorption activity in local activity maps. By integrating the current within these heat maps, the activity can be quantitatively compared across different 0.1 M (AM = Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Rb⁺, Cs⁺) electrolytes. The results suggest an increased HOR/H absorption activity with increasing cation size and decreasing hydration energy. This trend contrasts with bulk Pd and seems to stem from the highly active Pd sites, which are positioned in proximity to the Pd/Au border. The underlying Au substrate modified these Pd atoms' d-band structure. Independent LICT measurements were conducted to validate the cation trend, revealing an identical cation-activity correlation and confirming the results of the developed RC-SECM procedure.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information: XPS survey and Pd 3d high-resolution spectra (600 and 1000 ALD cycle samples); exemplary current versus time profile during the third pulse of the RC-SECM procedure; number of hydrogen molecule produced during third pulse of RC-SECM for 1600 ALD cycle Pd nanopillar sample; HOR/H-absorption local activity maps for 1600 ALD cycle sample and all electrolytes; Video of HOR/H-absorption local activity maps (first 5 ms, 1600 ALD cycle sample); Post-mortem AFM, EBSD, and texture plots as pole figures for the 1600 ALD cycle sample; LICT surface charge versus applied electrode potential for Pd_{ML}/Au(111) sample in all electrolytes.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Authors

Elena L. Gubanova

Physics of Energy Conversion and Storage, Technical University of Munich, James Franck Str. 1,
85748 Garching, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0003-3375-9833

Jan M. Macak

Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, 61200
Brno, Czech Republic; Center of Materials and Nanotechnologies, University of Pardubice, Nam.
Cs. Legii 565, 53002 Pardubice, Czech Republic; orcid.org/0000-0001-7091-3022

Aliaksandr S. Bandarenka

Physics of Energy Conversion and Storage, Technical University of Munich, James Franck Str. 1,
85748 Garching, Germany; Catalysis Research Center TUM, Ernst-Otto-Fischer-Str. 1, 85748
Garching, Germany; orcid.org/0000-0002-5970-4315

Authors

Christian M. Schott

Physics of Energy Conversion and Storage, Technical University of Munich, James Franck Str. 1,
85748 Garching, Germany

Julia Holl

Physics of Energy Conversion and Storage, Technical University of Munich, James Franck Str. 1,
85748 Garching, Germany

Raul Zazpe

Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, 61200
Brno, Czech Republic; Center of Materials and Nanotechnologies, University of Pardubice, Nam.
Cs. Legii 565, 53002 Pardubice, Czech Republic; orcid.org/0000-0003-0017-2323

Michael Kopp

Physics of Energy Conversion and Storage, Technical University of Munich, James Franck Str. 1,
85748 Garching, Germany

Ondřej Man

Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, 61200
Brno, Czech Republic; orcid.org/0000-0002-6032-1557

Sitaramanjaneya M. Thalluri

Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, 61200 Brno, Czech Republic; Center of Materials and Nanotechnologies, University of Pardubice, Nam. Cs. Legii 565, 53002 Pardubice, Czech Republic; orcid.org/0000-0001-5909-5305

Jhonatan Rodriguez-Pereira

Central European Institute of Technology, Brno University of Technology, Purkynova 123, 61200 Brno, Czech Republic; Center of Materials and Nanotechnologies, University of Pardubice, Nam. Cs. Legii 565, 53002 Pardubice, Czech Republic; orcid.org/0000-0001-6501-9536

Peter M. Schneider

Physics of Energy Conversion and Storage, Technical University of Munich, James Franck Str. 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

Kun-Ting Song

Physics of Energy Conversion and Storage, Technical University of Munich, James Franck Str. 1, 85748 Garching, Germany

Pekka Peljo

Research Group of Battery Materials and Technologies, Department of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Turku, 20014 Turun Yliopisto, Finland; orcid.org/0000-0002-1229-2261

Jerzy Jasielec

Research Group of Battery Materials and Technologies, Department of Mechanical and Materials Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Turku, 20014 Turun Yliopisto, Finland;
Department of Physical Chemistry and Modelling, Faculty of Materials Science and Ceramics, AGH University of Science and Technology, Al. Mickiewicza 30, 30-059 Kraków, Poland

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